

BENDING OF FIBRE-REINFORCED THERMOPLASTIC TUBES

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ABSTRACT

In this work, a bending process for wound fibre-reinforced thermoplastic tubes is presented. The setup consists of two modules, a heating unit and a rotary draw bending machine with modified tools. A test rig with IR heating module and a rotary unit is built and heating-up of a tube is investigated using a test rig with IR pyrometers and Pt100 resistance thermometers. The data is used for comparison and validation of a heat transfer simulation. Additionally, a method to measure the fibre angles of the outer layer of the wound tubes is developed and validated using the tube manufacturers data. Bending tests are performed on tubes with cross and parallel lay-up and different winding angles. The geometry of the manufactured tube bends and the fibre angles along the outer arc of the tube are measured and analysed.

1 INTRODUCTION

Tubular profiles are used for structural applications as well as parts of media leading systems. Due to different operation conditions, mechanical loads can be strongly oriented. Additionally, corrosion may appear, depending on the fluid inside and surrounding the tube. Manufacturing and further processing like bending and tube end finishing for metallic tubes are well investigated and applied. However, corrosion resistant metals are comparatively expensive and are limited for strongly oriented loads due to the isotropic material behaviour.

Thermoplastics are corrosion resistant and can be reinforced, using synthetical or natural fibres. AFPT GmbH is using endless fibre reinforced thermoplastic tapes to wind tubes, by locally melting the thermoplastic matrix and joining the tapes layer-wise. The winding angle of the tubes can be varied, i.e. adapted to purpose, and the lay-up can be parallel or cross ply. Additionally, the number of layers can be adapted to the application the tube is used for. A wound tube can either consist solely of layers of tape or the tape can be wound on a thermoplastic tube, called liner. Winding up on a liner improves leak tightness and raises the burst pressure of the tube. The tape has to be tensioned during winding. Therefore, the winding process does not allow manufacturing of curved profiles with strong curvature. For media leading systems, this drawback is solved using fittings, which leads to increased assembling cost and higher weight. To enable the usage of wound fibre-reinforced thermoplastic tubes (FRTT) without fittings, a bending process is developed to manufacture such parts.

Damage of the carbon fibres is to be prevented during the bending process. Therefore, the thermoplastic matrix has to be heated above melting temperature, so that relocation of the fibres during bending is possible. This means, the fibres can compensate the change in length caused by the bending through relocating.

The tubes used for the bending tests are wound using carbon fibre reinforced polyamide 6 (PA6) tapes with a fibre volume content of 48 %. The tape thickness is 0.19 mm and tape width is 12.5 mm. Different winding angles between 20 and 90 degrees were chosen for the tests. The outer diameter of the tubes is 22 mm with a wall thickness of 1 mm. With a target bending radius R of 44 mm, the ratio between bending radius and tube diameter, called bending ratio B , is 2. The bending machine is set up for a bending angle of 90 degrees.

2 SETUP OF THE BENDING PROCESS

The bending process is set up in two steps. First, the tube is heated up sectionally, as described in chapter 3. After exceeding the melting temperature of the matrix in the complete forming zone, the tube is transferred to the bending tools and the bending is performed. On the basis of the work of [1], a rotary draw bending (RDB) process is chosen, as schematically shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: rotary draw bending process for FRTT

One advantage of RDB is the capability, to bend tubes with constant bending radius and different bending angles, without the need of a tool change. One tool is capable to produce bendings from 0 to 180 degrees. Besides, the chosen RDB machine is able to bend in different directions.

The tube is clamped between the bend die and the outer clamp die. Both, bend die and outer clamp die, have an opening, which, in closed position, form a cavity with a diameter of 22 mm. The bending form is designed for a bending radius of 44 mm, with a clamping length of 44 mm. Bending form and outer clamp die have the same pivot, so the tube stays clamped during the bending. Bending form and outer clamp die are made of tool steel. A bending moment is induced through rotation of bend die and clamp die, which has to be countered by the pressure die. The pressure die is designed such, that it can move with zero slip parallel to the tube during bending. Movement of the pressure die prevents the rear edge from scratching along the tube, scraping the polyamide matrix off the tube. However, the support stays in contact with the same section of the tube. This means, that this part of the tube is cooled down on the outer side significantly. To reduce this effect, the support is made of PTFE, which reduces also adhesion of the tube to the pressure die. The Pressure die and outer clamp die close simultaneously and adjust the tube for bending. While bending the tube, the collet can be moved independently, so that a tensile force can be applied to the tube. This pretension reduces fibre wrinkling on the inner arc and preconsolidates the compound in the molten area.

To prevent the tubes cross section from deformations, such as ovalisation or formation of wrinkles, a mandrel is used. In contrast to rotary draw bending of metallic tubes, the mandrel is positioned such, that it supports the complete bending zone. The front end of the mandrel is located in front of the bending zone, so that the tube is not damaged during clamping. To insert the mandrel, a form release agent is applied on the mandrel, which lowers the frictional coefficient. In addition, the release agent enables the release of the mandrel after bending.

The molten matrix and the fibres have to be consolidated after they are heated up, because of the different coefficient of thermal expansion and the fibre movement. On the inner arc, consolidation is realised by the pressure between the mandrel and the bend form. On the outer arc, the pressure die consolidates in the forming zone and the tensioned fibres consolidate on the full length of the forming zone.

The bending is performed with a velocity of 48 degrees per second. After reaching end position, the tube is kept clamped until the surface temperature is below 100 °C. Then, the mandrel is pulled out and the tube cools down to ambient temperature.

3 HEATING-UP AND HEAT TRANSFER SIMULATION

Preliminary bending tests showed that the tubes have to be heated above melting temperature of the

thermoplastic matrix, to enable forming without damage. To maintain the possibility of the RDB process to bend arches with different bending angles, the heating zone has to be adjustable. In general, the heating zone has to have at least the length of the unrolled bending zone l_b , which can be calculated using the bending radius R of the neutral axis and the bending angle:

$$l_b = R \alpha \quad (1)$$

For the given geometry, a minimum heating length of 69.11 mm is required. To achieve a constant temperature distribution, four IR heaters are used for heating up of the tube. The heating zone can then be adjusted using reflector sheets, which shield the part of the tube, where no bending will take place. To enable the simulation of the process, a heating test is performed and temperature are measured for comparison with a heating-up simulation. For temperature measurement, different sensors are used. The temperature of the outer surface of the tube is measured using three Optris CS LT pyrometers, with a wavelength range between 8 and 14 μm . Between the silicone core and the tube, three Pt100 resistance thermometers are placed at corresponding positions to the pyrometers. The sensor placement is shown in Figure 2. A test rig is constructed to rotate the tube during heating, to homogenise the circumferential temperature field.

Figure 2: sensor placement for heating tests

Four Heraeus infrared (IR) golden eight heaters are placed every 90 degrees around the tube with a distance of 50 mm between the tubes surface and the heaters front. Each IR heater has a heating length of 50 mm, a maximum power of 200 W and a nominal emitted wavelength of 1.4 μm . According to Planck's law, the IR heater emits radiation above the nominal wavelength as well, and so, it emits radiation in the pyrometers measurement range. This leads to errors in IR measurement, due to reflection and direct radiation of the IR heaters. Therefore, a reference measurement is performed with two Pt100 resistance thermometers applied to the outer surface of the tube and a pyrometer measuring the peripheral temperature. A correction function is derived from the sensor data, which relates a correction factor to the pyrometers temperature value.

The simulation of the heating process is performed with the FE software ABAQUS. Symmetries are used, to minimise the calculation time. The IR heater is simulated as a planar 3D deformable plane with fixed temperature. FRTT and core are constructed as 3D deformable volumes with initial temperature. Quadratic heat transfer elements (DC3D20) are used to mesh all parts. Radiation of the IR heater is modelled as cavity radiation, with an emissivity of 0.95. Because the exact angles of radiation of the IR heaters are not known, rotation is not included in the simulation.

Material data is extracted from material data sheets and, in case of the FRTT, are calculated according to [2] using formulae for unidirectional composites. Input data for the analysis is shown in Table 1 for the FRTT.

	symbol	unit	value
orthotropic conductivity	$k_{FRTT,\parallel}$	$\left[\frac{mW}{mm K} \right]$	4.92
	$k_{FRTT,\perp}$	$\left[\frac{mW}{mm K} \right]$	0.39
density	ρ_{FRTT}	$\left[\frac{t}{mm^3} \right]$	1.8E-9

specific heat	c_{FRTT}	$\left[\frac{mJ}{tK}\right]$	1.7E+9
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Table 1: material properties of the FRTT

Thermal interaction is taken into account between FRTT and core. Due to a lack of experimental data regarding the contact conductance, the values shown in Table 1 are calculated using the formula proposed by [3] and experimental data provided by [4] [5]

	symbol	unit	value
gap conductance	$h_{Si/PA6}$	$\left[\frac{mW}{mm^2 K}\right]$	0.1

Table 2: thermal contact properties

A single transient heat transfer step is performed to calculate the resulting temperature at the tubes outer and inner surface. The nodal temperature at 4 nodes with corresponding coordinates to the position of the sensors is written out. The heating curve of the tube's outer and inner surface at the position of the sensors is shown for experiment and FE simulation in Figure 3.

Figure 3: comparison of simulation and test data

The results show, that determination of the gap conductance coefficient is crucial for the accuracy of the heat transfer simulation. Calculation of the coefficient proves to be difficult, experimental evaluation is indispensable. Looking at the start of the heating process, the experimental test data show a significantly shorter response time for the temperature at the inner surface, compared to simulation results. However, the slope of the test data curve is less than the simulation results. That means, heat is transferred through the tube faster than estimated by the simulation input data, but the amount of heat being transferred to the inner surface is less. This may be explained by the penetration depth of the radiation, which has not been taken into account for the simulation.

As a result, approximation of the heating process is possible via FE simulation and can be used for a rough estimation of the required thermal energy for heating up. However, a detailed analysis of the heating process requires further intensive investigation of the thermal interaction between tool and tube and inside the tube itself.

4 MEASUREMENT OF THE BENT TUBES

4.1 Fibre orientation

Fibre relocation has to take place, due to the high stiffness of the fibres and the comparatively low shear strength of the molten matrix. Two general mechanisms are distinguished. First, the fibre can move in radial direction of the tube, that is, the local fibre volume content will change through the tube's wall. The other mechanism is fibre realignment, concerning the fibre angle. This work focusses on the second mechanism. Radial fibre movement will be subject of subsequent publications.

A test rig is built to enable measurement of the fibre angle on the outer arc of the bent tubes. The principal design is shown in **Figure 4**. The fibre angle is defined as the angle between the tubes centre line and the tangent to the fibre.

Figure 4: measurement of the fibre angle

The camera is adjusted such, that the centreline of the lens is coincident with the centre point of the rotary disc and, in horizontal view, is on the bending plane of the tube. The tube is rotated in steps of 10 degrees and a picture is taken per step. A sector of the centre of each picture with a height of 10 mm is extracted, to analyse the fibre angle. To validate the measurement, the angle of tube sections, which were not bent, was measured and compared with the data provided by the manufacturer of the tubes. Additionally, the camera was misaligned in relation to the centre line of the straight tube stepwise up to 15 degrees, to quantify the measurement error, if the optical axis is not perpendicular to the tubes surface. The corresponding error to the misalignment angle is shown in Figure 5. Three points are chosen per picture as origin for the angle measurement, one in the centre of the picture and the other equidistant to the left and right of the origin. The arithmetic average of the three angles is used for investigation of the fibre movement.

Figure 5: validation of the angle measurement method

4.2 tube diameter

The diameter of the bent tube is measured at both sides of the bent tube at the straight part, using a FARO Edge measuring arm with a FARO Laser Line Probe mounted. Data generated in this measurement session will also be used to analyse the bending angle and deformation of the tubes cross section in subsequent studies. The contact-free measurement is validated by manual measurement of the diameter with a micrometer calliper. Therefore, the diameter is measured at three positions around the tubes circumference, with an offset of 120 degrees. The three values are then averaged and compared to the data of the laser line measurement. A maximum deviation of 2 % was found between the measurement techniques, so that for analysis, only the laser line results are considered.

5 RESULTS

5.1 Fibre angle displacement

The normalised fibre angle of tubes with different winding angles and cross layer lay-up is shown in Figure 6. The fibre angle is normalised using the initial fibre angle (IFA).

Figure 6: fibre angle of cross layer wound tubes after bending

The data show significant change in fibre orientation in the outer ply, in which the absolute change of the fibre angle depends on the IFA. A low IFA leads to less fibre alignment than a comparatively high fibre angle. For a IFA of 41.4 degrees (C45), the measured maximum change is 11.5 degrees, whereas it is 4.7 degrees for an IFA of 68 degrees (C70). This effect is explained with the force application while bending. Describing the composite as a combination of springs and dampers, concerning the compound materials properties, a theoretical IFA of 90 degrees will lead to a serial connection, while a fibre angle of 0 degrees will result in a parallel connection of matrix and fibre. Thus, due to the comparatively low tensile strength of the molten matrix, a low IFA will lead to plastic flow of the thermoplast rather than relocation of the fibre. However, at a fibre angle of nearly 90 degrees, the fibre will be tightened and therefore relocate. Comparison of the IFA and the measured fibre angle at the start and end of the bending shows, that at low IFA relocation of the fibre takes place mainly in the bending zone, while at high IFA, the fibre is already significantly relocated. This means, that fibre relocation in the tube also takes place before entering the bend die. With respect to this observation, it is distinguished between the bending zone and the forming zone, as shown in Figure 1.

In Figure 7, the resulting fibre angle for parallel layer wound tubes is shown. Comparison with the data for parallel layer wound tube shows, that the relocation of the fibre is similar regarding the fibre angle. In general, the change of fibre angle is more even at higher IFA, but not restricted to the bending zone. At low IFA, a significant change of the deviation from IFA is observed through the bending zone, but at the tangent point of the arc the fibre angle nearly matches the IFA. This is explained by the longitudinal stiffness of the fibres. With a low angle, the fibres are fixed closely to the bending zone due to cooled down matrix. At high fibre angles, i.e. a low slope, the fibre is wound over a larger section of the circumference in the forming zone. Thus, the fibre is able to relocate in the post bending zone.

Figure 7: fibre angle of parallel and cross layer wound tubes after bending

5.2 tube diameter

Analysis of the tube diameter in the pre and post bending zone shows distinct differences between the zones, if the molten zone is longer than the bending zone. This is illustrated for parallel layer wound tubes with a nominal fibre angle of 45 degrees and 55 degrees in Figure 8. In both cases, the matrix was molten over a length of 15 mm in the post bending zone. Measurement of the diameter after cooling down showed significant deviation from the nominal diameter. Inspection of the surface of the tubes revealed matrix, squeezed through the fibres, forming small matrix waves. Significant change in diameter due to heating is only observed at parallel layer wound tubes. Cross layer wound tubes are expected to be more stable against heating-up regarding the diameter, due to support of the crossing layers.

Figure 8: change in diameter at parallel layer wound tube

6 CONCLUSION

The rotary draw bending process is a stable and controllable process for manufacturing tube bends of wound fibre reinforced thermoplastic tubes. Investigation of the tubes showed, that consolidation of the molten matrix has to be guaranteed, to maintain geometric and hence mechanical properties. Optical inspection of the fibre orientation is a suitable method, to analyse the forming mechanisms in FRTT. It

showed that the assumed fibre-relocation takes place and is not dependant on the lay-up.

Fibre movement and relocation will be subject of further investigations. An existing model of the fibre relocation while bending will be validated using the bending test results.

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